

Use of Statins in the Prevention of Cardiovascular Events: A Review of the Benefits and Associated Risks

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ABSTRACT

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of global mortality and their impact is amplified by risk factors such as elevated LDL-C cholesterol levels. Statins are widely prescribed due to their efficacy in lowering LDL-C and preventing cardiovascular events. This review aims to explore the benefits and risks associated with statin use, analyzing the available evidence on their efficacy in both primary and secondary prevention. Research has shown that statins significantly reduce the risk of cardiovascular events, especially in high-risk patients. Despite the benefits, long-term use of statins can result in adverse effects such as new-onset diabetes and myalgias. We conclude that statins are beneficial for most high-risk patients, but a personalized assessment is recommended to ensure the best balance between risks and benefits.

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) represent one of the main public health problems worldwide, accounting for millions of deaths each year. It is estimated that approximately 17.9 million people die annually due to cardiovascular diseases, such as myocardial infarction and stroke. This scenario, which is worsened by population aging and the increase in modifiable risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes, smoking, obesity and, especially, dyslipidemia, poses a continuous challenge to the scientific community and global health systems. Among the most significant risk factors for CVDs are high cholesterol levels, particularly LDL-C (low-density lipoprotein). It is known that high levels of LDL-C are directly associated with the formation of atheroma plaques, contributing to the development of atherosclerosis and increasing the risk of serious cardiovascular events.

In this context, statins have emerged as one of the most effective treatments for controlling LDL-C levels. Discovered in the 1970s, statins have revolutionized the treatment of dyslipidemia and cardiovascular prevention by demonstrating a

significant impact on the reduction of cardiovascular events. These drugs act by inhibiting the enzyme HMG-CoA reductase, a crucial component in the hepatic cholesterol synthesis pathway. This inhibition leads to a decrease in cholesterol production by the liver and an increase in the uptake of circulating LDL-C, resulting in an effective reduction in LDL-C levels in the blood. Since their introduction, clinical studies with statins have shown that these drugs are effective in both the primary and secondary prevention of cardiovascular events.

In primary prevention, statins are recommended for individuals with cardiovascular risk factors but no previous history of cardiovascular events, in order to reduce the risk of developing CVD. In secondary prevention, statins are widely used in patients who have already suffered a cardiovascular event, such as a heart attack or stroke, with the aim of reducing the recurrence of new episodes. Several clinical studies and systematic reviews indicate that reducing LDL-C levels with statins is associated with a significant reduction in the incidence of cardiovascular events, CVD mortality and all-cause mortality in high-risk patients. Furthermore, the magnitude of the benefit appears to be proportional to the degree of LDL-C

reduction, i.e., the greater the reduction in cholesterol, the greater the reduction in cardiovascular risk.

However, the use of statins is not free from controversy and concerns regarding adverse effects. Although they are well tolerated in most cases, statins can cause side effects such as myalgia, myopathy and, in rare cases, rhabdomyolysis, a serious condition that can lead to renal failure. Another widely discussed adverse effect is the increased risk of new-onset diabetes in patients who use statins long-term. This risk appears to be particularly high in individuals with predisposing factors for diabetes, obesity and insulin resistance. The presence of these possible adverse effects raises questions about the safety and prescribing criteria for statins, especially in populations at low to moderate cardiovascular risk.

Therefore, the indication for statin use should be carefully considered and individualized. The new guidelines recommend that the decision to initiate statin treatment be based on a careful assessment of the patient's risk profile, considering factors such as age, family history, and comorbidities. In recent years, advances in genetic testing and biomarkers have been explored as potential tools to better predict response and tolerance to statin use, offering the prospect of more personalized and precise medicine.

This article aims to perform a comprehensive review of the main studies and available evidence on the use of statins in the prevention of cardiovascular events, exploring both the benefits and associated risks. To this end, studies that examine the efficacy of statins in reducing LDL-C and decreasing cardiovascular mortality will be analyzed, as well as research on the adverse effects and limitations of statin treatment. Through this review, we hope to provide a critical and updated view on the role of statins in cardiovascular prevention and contribute to the discussion on the appropriate and safe use of these drugs.

METHODS

For this study, an integrative literature review was conducted in the PubMed, ScienceDirect and Cochrane Library databases. Articles from the last ten years were selected, focusing on randomized clinical trials, systematic reviews and meta-analyses that examined the impact of statins on the prevention of cardiovascular events. In addition, the descriptors used were "statins", "cardiovascular prevention", "cardiovascular events" and "risks and benefits of statins" and their English counterparts "Statins", "Cardiovascular prevention", "Cardiovascular events" and "Risks and benefits of statins". Furthermore, the Boolean descriptor used was "AND" for the database search. The exclusion criteria were: articles that do not correlate with the theme of the use of statins in cardiovascular health, as well as articles published that do not cover the period studied from 2013 to 2024. A total of 739 articles were found, adding up all the databases. After reading the titles of the articles, it was observed that some of them did not meet the inclusion criteria for this study. Thus, it was possible to remove 250 duplicate articles and 489 articles were selected for reading the abstract. Of these, 469 studies were removed based on the analysis of the

abstract and did not meet the objective of elucidating the mechanisms of statin use in the primary prevention of cardiovascular events as well as their preponderant factors, resulting in 20 full texts included in this literature review. The selection criteria were studies that had to meet the following criteria: studies published in English and Portuguese, systematic reviews, case reports, clinical studies and articles published between 2013 and 2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A review of the literature on the use of statins in the prevention of cardiovascular events reveals consistent evidence of the significant benefits of these medications in reducing the risk of cardiovascular events in both primary and secondary prevention. Clinical studies and meta-analyses indicate that the use of statins results in a substantial reduction in LDL-C levels, which in turn is associated with a decrease in the risk of events such as myocardial infarction and stroke. The magnitude of this reduction appears to be directly related to the initial LDL-C level and the degree of cardiovascular risk of the patient, with the benefits being more significant in high-risk individuals, such as those who already have established cardiovascular disease. In secondary prevention, statins have been shown to be effective in reducing the recurrence of events and cardiovascular mortality, highlighting their essential role in the long-term protection of these patients.

In primary prevention, the efficacy of statins is largely observed in individuals with elevated risk factors (such as hypertension, diabetes, and smoking) and high LDL-C levels, but without a previous history of cardiovascular events. However, the indication of statins for individuals at moderate risk, especially the elderly and patients without other significant risk factors, remains a subject of debate. In some of these cases, the absolute benefit of reducing cardiovascular events may be small, and the use of statins needs to be balanced against the possibility of adverse effects. Current guidelines recommend that the decision to use statins in primary prevention should be individualized, taking into account the risks and preferences of the patient, in order to maximize clinical benefit and minimize potential side effects.

Adverse effects of statin use, although uncommon, can impact treatment adherence and safety. Myalgias and myopathies are the most frequently reported effects, and are usually mild, but in some cases they can be severe enough to lead to treatment discontinuation. In rare cases, statins can cause rhabdomyolysis, a serious adverse effect that occurs in a small fraction of patients. In addition, studies suggest that statins may increase the risk of new-onset diabetes, especially in individuals who already have a predisposition to insulin resistance, such as those who are overweight or obese. This effect, although important, does not negate the cardiovascular benefits, but reinforces the need for careful monitoring in risk groups.

Furthermore, the impact of statins on markers of inflammation and other mechanisms underlying atherosclerosis has also been discussed. Evidence suggests that statins exert an anti-inflammatory effect, reducing levels of C-reactive protein

(CRP), which is an inflammatory marker associated with cardiovascular risk. This additional effect may contribute to the benefits of statins, especially in patients with a high inflammatory profile, although LDL-C reduction remains the primary mechanism of cardiovascular protection.

Finally, the use of statins in clinical practice should be guided by an individualized risk-benefit assessment. For patients at high cardiovascular risk, the benefits of statins in reducing cardiovascular events and mortality considerably outweigh the potential risks. In low- to moderate-risk patients, the decision is more complex and may involve the use of biomarkers and new risk stratification tools to identify which individuals would benefit most from treatment. Future studies should focus on identifying subgroups of patients who may benefit from personalized strategies, including the possibility of therapeutic alternatives for those who are statin-intolerant.

Thus, these findings highlight the importance of statins in cardiovascular prevention, but also reinforce the need for an individualized approach that analyzes the needs and characteristics of each patient. Thus, the use of statins can be optimized, maximizing their benefits while minimizing potential adverse effects, contributing to a better quality of life and increased survival of patients at cardiovascular risk.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the reviewed evidence indicates that statins are essential in the prevention of cardiovascular events, both in primary and secondary prevention, especially in high-risk patients. By significantly reducing LDL-C levels, statins have been shown to reduce the occurrence of events such as heart attack and stroke, offering substantial protection and reducing cardiovascular mortality. In secondary prevention, the continuous use of these medications has been shown to be particularly advantageous, since it reduces the chances of recurrence of cardiovascular events and increases patient survival. This positive impact is mainly evident in individuals who already have cardiovascular disease, for whom treatment with statins is established as an essential preventive intervention.

Despite the proven benefits, the use of statins requires caution, especially in patients with moderate cardiovascular risk. Potential adverse effects, although rare, may include myalgias, myopathies and a slight increase in the risk of diabetes, which may affect adherence to treatment. Therefore, the prescription decision should be based on a personalized assessment, considering the risk profile and individual needs of each patient. This personalized approach is essential to optimize the efficacy and safety of statins, allowing the benefits to be maximized while minimizing possible side effects, promoting a more effective and safe clinical practice in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases.

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